

DIFFERENCES IN SALT TOLERANCE OF TWO POPULATIONS OF *SEDOBASSIA SEDOIDES*

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Annotation. In presence of global warming and climate aridification, salinity levels of agricultural soils increase. To restore them, plantings of halophytes such as *Sedobassia sedoides* are used. We compared the responses of two populations of this species to salinity stress, which showed that plants of St population faster accumulate Na^+ in its tissues compared with the plants of El population. Plants from both populations demonstrated a decrease in the K^+ content when grown under saline conditions. St plants have reduced CO_2 assimilation after one week of salinity stress. For plants of El population in saline conditions an increase in the proline content and a decrease in tissue water content were found, which were not observed in St plants, indicating greater resistance of St plants to salinity.

Keywords: *sedobassia sedoides*, salinity, salt stress, intraspecific variability.

Introduction

In the context of global warming and climate aridification, the quality of agricultural soils is deteriorating, in particular, salinization is increasing [1]. Therefore, it is important to study the adaptation of plants to conditions of ionic and osmotic stress in order to develop a strategy for crop protection. *Sedobassia sedoides* is a halophyte, which demonstrates high intraspecific variability in resistance to salinity and drought [2], with different populations possibly having different mechanisms of acclimation to unfavorable environmental factors. Studying the differences between *S. sedoides* populations will allow not only to select the most resistant forms for cultivation in various extreme conditions, but also to study a wide range of physiological responses.

Materials and methods

Seeds of two populations (St and El) of *Sedobassia sedoides* (Pall.) Freitag & G. Kadereit (Chenopodiaceae) were collected in the natural conditions of the Caspian Depression on soils with different levels of salinity. For laboratory experiments, *S. sedoides* seeds were germinated in distilled water. Seedlings aged 3–4 days were transplanted onto perlite soaked in 50% Hoagland nutrient solution. Plants were grown under fluorescent lamps at a PAR quantum flux density of $200 \mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{s}$, 16-hour photoperiod, and a temperature of 25°C . To create a moderate salinity for the salt-tolerant *S. sedoides* plants, salinization experiments used a 200 mM NaCl solution that was poured into trays with the plant cuvettes. Plants watered with a 50% Hoagland solution were used as a control. Measurements were carried out one and three weeks after the transfer of experimental groups to 200 mM NaCl.

To determine dry biomass, plant samples were dried for two days at 80°C . The level of Na^+ and K^+ in photosynthetic organs was determined in an aqueous extract of the sample (100 mg)

using an atomic absorption spectrometer (Hitachi 207, Japan). The content of free proline was determined using an acidic ninhydrin reagent [3], the results were calculated per 1 g of dry mass.

The gas exchange parameters were determined using an infrared gas analyzer (IRGA) in the CIRAS-3 (PP Systems, USA), which determines the difference in CO₂ and H₂O content between the air that has passed through the chamber with the leaf (in the experimental cuvette) and the air in the control cuvette. The software in the device calculates the visible CO₂ assimilation (A, μmol/m²*s) and transpiration (E, mmol/m² *s) based on these values [4.5.6]. The measurements were carried out at photon flux of 1800 μmol/m²* s and a red, green and blue ratio of 38:37:25.

All experiments had at least three biological replicates. SigmaPlot12.0 software was used for factorial (ANOVA) analysis. The table (table 1) shows the mean values and their standard errors. Differences were considered reliable at P < 0.05.

Results

In control, differences between *S. sedoides* populations were observed only in shoot length. Shoots of plants from the St population grow on average 3-4 cm longer than those of plants from the El population.

As a result of one week of salinity, sodium content in the shoots of the St plants was 5 times higher, while in the shoots of the El plants it was 3 times higher (Table 1). In addition, after 3 weeks of 200 mM NaCl exposure, sodium content in shoots of El plants increased 8 times compared to the control, and almost 2 times compared to the effect of one week of salt stress. The plants of St population showed a decrease in CO₂ assimilation, which became less pronounced after 3 weeks of cultivation. El plants showed a decrease in water content under the influence of one week of salinity. However, later, due to shoot sclerotization, the water content of the control plants has decreased to that of the plants subjected to salt stress.

Table 1. Response of different populations of *Sedobassia sedoides* to salinization.

Parameters	<i>Sedobassia sedoides</i>			
	St		El	
	Control	200mM NaCl	Control	200mM NaCl
One week				
Shoot length, cm	13.0 ± 1.4 ^a	12.3 ± 0.5 ^a	15.0 ± 0.8 ^a	15.5 ± 0.8 ^a
Raw biomass, g	0.91 ± 0.08 ^a	0.74 ± 0.11 ^a	1.14 ± 0.11 ^a	1.10 ± 0.28 ^a
Water content	10.9 ± 0.5 ^{ab}	10.0 ± 0.3 ^{ab}	11.3 ± 0.4 ^a	9.7 ± 0.3 ^b
Na content, mmol/g	0.6 ± 0.03 ^a	3.0 ± 0.12 ^b	0.8 ± 0.08 ^{a,b}	2.4 ± 0.43 ^{a,b}
K content, mmol/g	1.8 ± 0.08 ^a	1.6 ± 0.06 ^a	2.2 ± 0.17 ^a	1.8 ± 0.06 ^a
Proline content, mmol/g	0.016 ± 0.001 ^a	0.014 ± 0.001 ^a	0.015 ± 0.001 ^a	0.015 ± 0.001 ^a
A (CO ₂ assimilation), μmol/m ² *s	19.41 ± 1.32 ^a	9.55 ± 0.58 ^b	17.98 ± 3.824 ^a	11.41 ± 1.24 ^a
E (transpiration), mmol/m ² *s,	4.42 ± 0.57 ^a	2.15 ± 0.16 ^a	4.40 ± 0.86 ^a	2.64 ± 0.04 ^a
Three weeks				
Shoot length, cm	29.8 ± 0.4 ^a	29.7 ± 0.2 ^a	26.0 ± 0.4 ^b	26.3 ± 0.9 ^b
Raw biomass, g	3.30 ± 0.50 ^a	3.27 ± 0.26 ^a	2.28 ± 0.04 ^a	1.86 ± 0.20 ^a

Water content	7.0 ± 0.1 ^a	7.1 ± 0.1 ^a	6.6 ± 0.3 ^a	6.5 ± 0.1 ^a
Na content, mmol /g	0.7 ± 0.08 ^a	3.9 ± 0.11 ^b	0.5 ± 0.04 ^a	4.4 ± 0.10 ^b
K content, mmol /g	2.4 ± 0.16 ^a	1.3 ± 0.03 ^b	2.1 ± 0.03 ^a	1.1 ± 0.29 ^b
Proline content, mmol /g	0.012 ± 0.003 ^a	0.017 ± 0.001 ^a	0.016 ± 0.001 ^a	0.025 ± 0.001 ^b
A (CO ₂ assimilation), µmol /m ² *s	17.98 ± 1.09 ^a	12.68 ± 0.54 ^a	17.10 ± 0.59 ^a	9.57 ± 0.56 ^a
E (transpiration), mmol/m ² *s,	5.69 ± 0.35 ^a	3.62 ± 0.19 ^a	6.62 ± 0.42 ^a	3.29 ± 0.19 ^a

After a three week long 200 mM NaCl exposure, accumulation of proline in El plants was observed, which has not been found in St plants, indicating a lower resistance of plants in the El population to salinity. In addition, both populations showed a 2-fold decrease in the K⁺ content in biomass.

Conclusions:

1. Under control conditions, the two populations differed solely in shoot length; under the influence of salinity, plants of the St population showed a faster accumulation of Na⁺ and temporary decrease in CO₂ assimilation.
2. Plants from both populations demonstrated a decrease in the K⁺ content when grown under saline conditions.
3. Plants of the El population demonstrated lower salt tolerance, as evidenced by water loss and proline accumulation under saline conditions.

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REFERENCES

1. Eswar D., Karuppusamy R., Chellamuthu S. Drivers of soil salinity and their correlation with climate change //Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability. – 2021. – T. 50. – C. 310-318.
2. Rakhmankulova Z. F. et al. Different responses of two ecotypes of C 3–C 4 xero-halophyte *Bassia sedoides* to osmotic and ionic factors of salt stress //Russian Journal of Plant Physiology. – 2016. – T. 63. – C. 349-357.
3. Bates L.S., Waldren R.P., Teare I.D. Rapid determination of free proline for water stress studies // Plant Soil. 1973 V. 39 P. 205
4. Buck A.L. New Equations for Computing Vapor Pressure and Enhancement Factor // Journal of Applied Meteorology. 1981. V. 20., № 12. - P. 1527–1532.
5. Caemmerer S. von, Farquhar G.D. Some relationships between the biochemistry of photosynthesis and the gas exchange of leaves // Planta. 1981. V. 153, № 4. - P. 376–387.
6. CIRAS-3 Portable Photosynthesis System Operation Manual